

Annex B.3 – Antimicrobial resistance in *Campylobacter*

Annex to:

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(A)

(B)

Figure 1 - Trends in ciprofloxacin (CIP), erythromycin (ERY) and tetracycline (TET) resistance in *Campylobacter jejuni* from (A) broilers and (B) fattening turkeys, 2014–2023.

Trends in resistance to Ciprofloxacin, Erythromycin and Tetracycline in *C. coli* from broilers, 2014-2022

Resistance to: Ciprofloxacin (CIP) Erythromycin (ERY) Tetracycline (TET)

Figure 2 - Trends in ciprofloxacin (CIP), erythromycin (ERY) and tetracycline (TET) resistance in *Campylobacter coli* from broilers 2014–2023

A)

Distribution of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values related to erythromycin resistance in *C. jejuni* from pigs and calves, 2023

B)

Distribution of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values related to erythromycin resistance in *C. coli* from pigs and calves, 2023

B)

Distribution of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values related to erythromycin resistance in *C. jejuni* from broilers and turkeys, 2022

C)

Distribution of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values related to erythromycin resistance in *C. coli* from broilers and turkeys, 2022

Figure 3 - Distribution of minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values related to erythromycin resistance in (A) *C. jejuni* from fattening pigs and cattle under 1 year of age and (B) *C. coli* from fattening pigs and cattle under 1 year of age, (C) *C. jejuni* from broilers and fattening turkeys, (D) *C. coli* from broilers and fattening turkeys, in reporting MSs, the United Kingdom (Northern Ireland), and non-MSs, 2022 and 2023

TEXT BOX: Country-level findings on high-level resistance to erythromycin

Summary of the country-level findings on high-level resistance to erythromycin in *Campylobacter jejuni* and *C. coli* isolates

In 2023, the highest level of erythromycin resistance (MIC > 512 mg/L) was obtained in several *Campylobacter coli* isolates from fattening pigs distributed among 23 out of the 30 reporting countries. Nine of the 23 countries reported a single isolate with MIC > 512 mg/L (Croatia, Estonia, Finland, France, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Norway and Sweden). Ten countries reported less than 20 *C. coli* isolates from fattening pigs with the highest level of erythromycin resistance (Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Denmark, Italy, Malta, the Netherlands, Poland and Slovakia). The largest numbers of *C. coli* isolates from fattening pigs with the highest erythromycin resistance level were reported by Portugal (47 isolates), Romania (32 isolates), Spain (30 isolates), and Germany (20 isolates). Also in 2023, *C. jejuni* isolates from cattle under 1 year of age with the highest level of erythromycin resistance (MIC > 512 mg/L) were obtained from samples from Belgium (five isolates), Italy (two isolates) and Germany (one isolate). In 2023, highest level erythromycin-resistant *C. coli* isolates from cattle under 1 year of age were reported by eight out of 12 reporting countries. Notably, in 2023, the highest level of erythromycin resistance was detected in a very high proportion of the erythromycin-resistant *C. coli* isolates from cattle under 1 year of age (112 out of a total of 147 erythromycin-resistant isolates). Sixty and 31 out of the 112 *C. coli* isolates from cattle under 1 year of age with the highest level of erythromycin resistance were reported by Belgium and the Netherlands, respectively. Additionally, France and Germany reported seven and eight isolates, respectively, while five other countries reported one or two isolates with the highest level of erythromycin resistance.

C. jejuni isolates from broilers with the highest level of erythromycin resistance (MIC > 512 mg/L) were obtained in 2022 from samples from Romania (nine isolates). Also in 2022, two of the three *C. jejuni* isolates from fattening turkeys with highest-level resistance to erythromycin were also detected in Romania, and the other was detected in Poland. Highest-level erythromycin-resistant *C. coli* isolates from broilers were reported by eight out of 28 reporting countries. Twenty-four out of 43 *C. coli* isolates from broilers with the highest level of erythromycin resistance were reported by Portugal (14 isolates) and Romania (10 isolates). Additionally, Malta and Spain reported seven and six isolates, respectively, while the remaining countries reported one or two isolates. Notably, in 2022, the highest level of erythromycin resistance was detected in a high proportion of the erythromycin-resistant *C. coli* isolates from fattening turkeys (117 out of a total of 249 erythromycin-resistant isolates), among six out of 11 reporting countries. The majority of the highest-level resistant isolates were reported among four MSs, specifically Romania (46 isolates), Portugal (34 isolates), Germany (20 isolates), and Poland (12 isolates). The remaining two MSs who detected highest-level erythromycin resistance in *C. coli* isolates from fattening turkeys reported three (Spain) and two (Ireland) isolates with MIC > 512 mg/L.